

FORMULATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF HERBAL SOAP**Makwana Rajeshree^{*1}, Mona Sutha², Ankur Patel³, Anamika Sharma⁴**^{*1}Sardar Patel College of Pharmacy, Bakrol, Gujarat, India.²Indubhai Patel College of Pharmacy and Research Centre, Dharmaj, Gujarat,³Sardar Patel College of Pharmacy, Bakrol, Gujarat, India.⁴Bkp College Deori Sagar M.P, India.***Corresponding Author: Makwana Rajeshree**

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ABSTRACT

The herbal soap was formulated by using leaf of neem, Aloe Vera, Tulsi, ayurvedic cosmetics is very helpful and does not give it side effects. Ayurvedic cosmetics are also known as herbal cosmetics. All herbal ingredients are easily available in market of surrounding areas. Tulsi gives many benefits for the skin like keep clean the skin. Treat acne lightens skin tone vit -c and turmeric also used. Herbal soap preparation is a medicine or drug like medicinal properties like antibacterial antifungal bring the skin and may property. The crude drug which used in the soap preparation is given many properties medicine or cosmetics. The plant used in soap preparation is able to soft the skin epidermis enhances greater penetration remove acne as well as promotes healing and resolution in quickly in time.

KEYWORDS: Aloe Vera, Herbal Soap, Cosmetics, Tulsi.**1. INTRODUCTION****1.1 HERBAL SOAP**

Soap is defined as a substance which dissolves in water, thus forming a lather, and used as a cleansing agent. Soap preparation mainly content neem, tulsi, vit-E, aloe vera and glycerine soap base and Rose Water. This content gives it common property or many positive effects on the skin. Neem is the mostly effective because it's shown many properties like antibacterial antifungal or many skin problem. It gives many properties like deep clean the skin, treat acne, lightens skin tone.

People have been using neem tree as a source of medicine since time immemorial. Numerous compounds can be found from different parts of neem, such as its seed, bark, and leaf.

TYPE OF SOAP

- ❖ Cleaning soap
- ❖ Personal soap
- ❖ Perfume soap
- ❖ Beauty soap
- ❖ Medicated soap
- ❖ Glycerine soap

- ❖ Transparent soap
- ❖ Liquid soap

Benefits of soap

- ❖ Protects the skin from infections.
- ❖ Prevents sun burn
- ❖ They also protect the skin from inflammation, redness, irritation
- ❖ Neem and aloe vera with clearing bacteria, fungus, and microbes that cause acne and eruption of the skin.
- ❖ Herbal soap contain the natural goodness of nature, and this make them nourishing for your skin.
- ❖ Glycerine soap base also protects the skin which is sensitive and delicate, and when herbal soap are used, you can be sure that the glycerine content is high absorbing water in the air and ensuring the skin remain soft and healthy.

❖ MATERIALS

Figure 1.1: Types of herbal formulations.

1.2 SKIN

The skin of the average human being covers an area of about 2 square meter and weighs 4.5-5 kg, about 16 % of body weight. It also receives 1/3 rd of the total blood supply. The skin is a most extensive and readily accessible organ of the human body. Most topical preparation are meant to be applied to the skin and hence basic knowledge of skin and its physiological function and biochemistry is very important for designing topical formulations. The pH of the skin varies from 4 to 5.6. Sweat and fatty acids secreted from sebum influence the pH of the skin surface. It is suggested that acidity of the skin helps in preventing the growth of pathogens and other organisms.

1.3 ACNE

Acne is a long-term skin disease that arises when hair sacs are blocked with departed skin cells. It is characterized by the formation of inflammatory and non-inflammatory lesions of the hair follicles and /or sebaceous glands commonly referred to as the pilosebaceous unit. A slight degree of acne is typical at puberty, but a serious case can cause unsightly appearance and leaves scarring in many cases even after treatment. The common name for acne is Acne vulgaris. 70% - 80% of patients affected by this are aged 11-25 years old. In practical terms, acne may be grouped in terms of severity of the symptoms; i.e. mild, moderate and severe.

- **Inflammatory lesions-** It manifests themselves as papules, pustules, cysts and nodules. Acne vulgaris is generally characterized by formation of seborrhea, comedones, inflammatory lesions and presence of bacteria in the follicular canal and sebum production.
- **Non inflammatory lesions-** It is categorized as open comedons (blackheads) and closed comedons (white heads).

1.3.1 Types of acne

➤ Acne rosacea

It is a skin disease of adults. Rosacea usually acts upon the central third of the face, especially the nose with periodic aggravation and relief. The symptoms may come and go and the skin may be clear for weeks, months, or years and then may emerge time and again. Often affected by women in which blood vessels of the face enlarge indicating a flushed appearance. Rosacea is a common, chronic, incurable, adult acne-like skin condition that is easily controllable and curable medically. Rosacea incline to develop in certain stages and causes to create inflammation of the skin of the face, especially the forehead, cheeks, nose, as well as chin. Symptoms and signs of rosacea are: Redness of the face, tiny red pimples and fine red lines on the facial skin. An enlarged, bulbous red nose. Eye problems, like swollen, red eyelids and conjunctivitis.

➤ Acne vulgaris

Hickey, pimple, zit A small inflamed elevation of the skin; a pustule or papules which are common symptoms in acne. The most common form of acne; usually affects people from puberty to young adult hood. Difference between a pimple and acne: Unlike common acne, rosacea is not primarily a disease of teenagers but occurs most often in adults (ages 30-50), especially in those with fair skin. Different than acne, there are usually no blackheads or whiteheads in rosacea. Certain people get one or two spots off and on while others get frequent eruption of spots with lots of pus-filled pimples indicates acne which is a chronic or prolonged condition that affects many teens and adults. More or less all human beings in the world gets pimples at some point of time sooner the body enter into puberty stage at the age of 12, there commence to release hormones and start to function in the bodies of man or woman irrespectively and at this juncture food or pollution, ought to upset hormonal balance thereafter.

Figure 1.2: Types of Acne.

Pimples or spots come out when the skin produces much more oil, causes breeding bacteria which clog the existing pores creating swelling and redness on the skin. Pimples are not at all contagious. Whiteheads – Remain under the surface of skin and are very small.

- **Pustules** – (pimples or zits) are red at the bottom level consisting of pus at its top and can be looked on the surface of the skin.
- **Nodules** – Clearly visible on the surface of the skin. They are painful, large, solid pimples existing deeply in the skin and can be seen on the skin surface.
- **Cysts** – Clearly visible on the surface of the skin. They are deeply rooted, painful and pus filled and easily prone to form scars.
- **Blackheads** – Vividly look black and rise to the surface of the skin but are not formed due to dirt. Black heads are not black because of dirt they are black in color. Generally, air oxidizes the protein called keratin.

- **Papules** – They are small tender pink bumps which are clearly seen on the skin.

1.3.2 Sequence of events in acne

Acne happens when hair follicles become clogged with dead skin cells and a sticky substance called sebum is produced by the sebaceous glands. This excess sebum causes skin cells to stick together inside the follicles, causing an obstruction. Hormones, environmental factors as well as genetic susceptibility may be the cause for acne. This leads to a comedone. Once bacteria nestle in to the clogged pore or comedone, they release factors that cause inflammation. This causes comedones to turn in to the pimples and pustules. Some acne lesions become so inflamed that they rupture, which forms nodules. Due to confluence of affected glands nodules form cysts which may result in to scar formation after healing.

Figure 1.3: Pathophysiology of Acne.

1.3.3 Treatment of Acne

Topical as well as systemic therapy is available for the treatment of acne. While traditional treatments in the inflammatory phase are topical and systemic antibiotics acting as both antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory agents, modern acne therapy has been designed to interrupt the pathogenic pathway at one or more points. Treatment of acne depends on its condition and degree of severity which may vary from a mild non inflammatory comedons to an inflammatory papule or pustule. This usually signifies the presence of *Propionibacterium acnes*. The excessive use of antibiotics for long periods has led to the increased resistance in acne causing

bacteria i.e. *Staphylococcus epidermis*, *Propionibacterium acne* against a number of antibiotics used to treat acne. World health organization (WHO) noted that majority of the world's population depends on traditional medicine for primary health care.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS^[1,3]

2.1. MATERIALS

In this herbal face serum we used different types of herbal materials such as Aloe vera gel, Olive oil, Neem oil, Glycerin, Coconut oil, Vitamin-E capsule, Extract of basil and Rose water.

Aloe vera gel

Figure 2.1: Aloe-vera gel and Plant.

➤ **Common Names:** Aloe indica Royle, True Aloe, Barbados Aloe, Indian Aloe

➤ **Vernacular Name**

Sanskrit - Aphala

Hindi - Matlab

Tamil- Katralai

Malayalam – kattarvazha.

➤ **Family**

Aloeaceae

➤ **Synonyms**

Aloe barbedensis mill, Aloe barbedensis. Chinensis Haw, Aloe chinensis (Haw.) Baker.

➤ **Taxonomy**

Aloe Vera is a succulent plant species of the genus Aloe. An evergreen perennial, grows wild in tropical climates around the world and is cultivated for agricultural and medicinal uses.

➤ **Description**

A perennial herb with short stem and shallow root system. Leaves: fleshy in rosettes, sessile very much horny prickles on the margin, convex below.

➤ **Distribution**

Aloe Vera grows in arid climate and is widely distributed in Africa, India and other arid areas. The species is frequently cited as being used in herbal medicine.

➤ **Chemical constituents**

Barbaloin, Chrysophanol glycoside, Aglycone, Aloemodin, Aloesone and Aloesin.

➤ **Medicinal properties**

Bitter, sweet, cooling, anthelmintic, carminative, stomachic.

➤ **Uses**

Aloe vera has been used for centuries for its healing properties and is commonly used in skin care products. Here are some of the benefits of aloe vera for the skin

- **Anti-ageing properties:** Aloe vera is rich in antioxidants and can help slow down the signs of ageing. It can help improve skin elasticity and reduce the appearance of fine lines and wrinkles.
- **Treats acne:** Aloe vera has antibacterial properties that can help treat acne. It can help reduce inflammation and prevent the formation of acne scars.
- **Reduces dark circles:** Aloe vera has a cooling effect on the skin and can help reduce puffiness and dark circles under the eyes.
- **Improves skin tone:** Aloe vera can help improve skin tone and texture. It can help reduce the appearance of blemishes, scars, and dark spots.
- **Moisturizes the skin:** Aloe vera is a great moisturizer and can help hydrate the skin without leaving it oily or greasy.
- **Soothes sunburn:** Aloe vera is known for its ability to soothe sunburned skin. It can reduce inflammation and redness caused by sunburn and help the skin heal faster.

2.1.2. NEEM

Figure 2.2: Neem.

- ❖ **Biological Name** – Azadirachta indica
- ❖ **Family** – Mahogany
- ❖ **Synonym** – Holy tree

- ❖ **Uses**- Neem leave have effective and extremely good for the skin. It also clear acne, pimples and help detoxify the skin cells of pollutants.

2.1.6. Basil (Tulsi)

Figure 2.3: Basil.

➤ **Synonyms**

Holy basil, Tulasei, Tulsi, Tulasi

➤ **Biological sources**

Tulsi consists of the fresh and dried leaves of *Ocimum* species like *Ocimum sanctum* L. and *Ocimum basilicum* L. etc.

➤ **Family**

Lamiaceae

➤ **Class**

Magnoliopsida

➤ **Odour**

Lamiales

➤ **Taste**

Astringent

➤ **Species**

Ocimum canum (Ram Tulasi or kali Tulsi), *Ocimum kalimand*, *Ocimum scharicum*.

- **Uses:** Basil, also known as Tulsi, is a popular herb in Ayurvedic medicine and is believed to have a wide range of health benefits, including for the skin. Some of the benefits of basil for skin include.

- **Anti-ageing properties:** Basil contains antioxidants that can help prevent damage to the skin from free radicals, which can contribute to premature ageing of the skin.
- **Hydrating properties:** Basil contains essential oils that can help hydrate the skin, keeping it soft and supple.
- **Brightening properties:** Basil contains natural oils that can help brighten the skin, reducing the appearance of dark spots and blemishes.
- **Anti-inflammatory properties:** Basil contains antioxidants and anti-inflammatory compounds that can help reduce inflammation on the skin, which can help soothe irritated or inflamed skin.
- **Antimicrobial properties:** Basil has natural antimicrobial properties that can help fight against bacteria and fungi on the skin, which can help prevent acne and other skin infections.

2.2. METHODS OF PREPARATION^[10]

Take 14gm of Neem powder in a beaker and add 6gm of Tulsi, 10gm of aloe vera, 4 capsule vit-E and oil 5drops Rose water. Then mixed all ingredients for 2 to 3 min. Used double heat method for the melting of glycerine soap base. After melting the glycerine soap base and add the previously mixed ingredients then stir it properly. Then transfer this mixture into the soap container for moulding. Check the final product for packaging

Table 2.1: Final Formulation.

Sr No	INGREDIENTS	F1	F2	F3	USES
1	Soap Base(gm)	25	20	22	Remove dirt from skin
2	Aloe Vera(gm)	10	9	10	Anti-oxidant activity
3	Neem(gm)	15	10	14	Antibacterial activity
4	Tulsi(gm)	8	5	6	Antimicrobial activity
5	Almond oil(ml)	1	2	1.5	Anti-oxidant activity
6	Rose water(drops)	5	5	5	Perfume
7	Vitamin E(capsule)	5	3	4	Anti – oxidant activity

F3 formulation is good compare to other trials because it's stability and therapeutic effect is better than other

formulation due to high quantity of vitamin-E which act as anti-oxidant therefore it's provide good stability.

➤ Procedure

2.3. Experimental work

3. EVALUATION PARAMETERS^[3,6]

3.1 Physical parameters

The Color and appearance of the formulation was observed visually. The formulation procedure uniform distribution of extracts. This test was confirmed by visual appearance and by touch.

3.2 pH value

a) pH meter

A pH meter was calibrated using a standard buffer solution pH 7 according to the manufacturer's instructions. After the calibration takenearly 1 ml of the face serum was properly weighed and dissolve in 50 ml of distilled water and the sample should be sufficient to immerse the electrode of the pH meter. Rinse the pH electrode with distilled water to remove any residue from previous measurements. Gently blot it dry with a clean tissue. Immerse the clean electrode into the unknown sample solution. Ensure that the electrode is fully submerged and that it does not touch the sides or bottom of the container. Allow the pH meter reading to stabilize. Once the pH reading stabilize, record the pH value. The skin has an acidic range and the pH of the skin serum should be in the range of 4.1-6.7.

b) pH strip

Take a pH strip and deep into the sample solution. Make sure the entire strip is submerged and remains in the solution for a few seconds to allow the color to develop.

After a few seconds remove the pH strip form the solution, ensuring that may excess liquid drains off. The pH strip will undergo a color change depending on the pH of the solution. The strip will typically have a color chart or indicator bands that correspond to different pH levels. Compare the color of the strip with provided chart to determine the pH value. Match the color of the pH strip with closest color on the chart. The corresponding color will indicate the pH value of sample solution.

3.3 Irritation Test

The Herbal Soap composition was subjected to a skin irritant test. There is no redness in the preparation. The condition was observed for a period of 24 hrs.

3.4 Foaming ability

Foaming ability was determined by using cylinder shake method bristle 40ml of the formulation soap solution was placed graduate cylinder. It was covered with hand and shaken 10 times the total volume of the foam content after 1 min of shaking recovered foam stability was evaluated by recording the foam volume after 1 min and 4 min is 80 to 93 ml foam formed.

3.5 Foaming Height

0.5 grams of sample of soap was taken dispersed in 25 ml distilled water. Then, transferred it in to 100ml measuring cylinder; volume was make up to 50 ml with water. 25 strokes were given and stand till aqueous

volume measured up to 50 ml and measured the foam height, above the aqueous volume was measured.

3.6 Foaming Retention

25 ml of the 1% soap solution was taken in to a 100 ml graduated measuring cylinder. The cylinder was covered with hand and shaken 10 times. The volume of foam at 1 minute intervals for 4 minutes was Recorded.

Table 4.1: Physical Evaluation.

Sr. No	Test	First Trial	Second Trial	Third trial
1	Colour	Light Green	Light Green	Dark Green
2	Clarity	Non –Transperent	Non – Transperent	Non – Transperent
3	Texture	Sticky	Non sticky	Non sticky
4	Odour	Bitter smell	Bitter smell	Good smell

4.2 pH Value

The pH of F1 formulation was found to be 7 ± 0.1 . As the skin having an acidic pH around 4.1-6.7, this range of

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Physical Evaluation

The Colour and appearance of the formulation was observed visually. The formulation procedure uniform distribution of extracts.

formulation is suitable for skin. For below all batches F3 batch having optimum pH so we select F3 batch.

Table 4.2: pH value.

Sr.No	Formulation	PH reading $SD \pm 3n$
1	F1	7 ± 0.1
2	F2	8.5 ± 0.1
3	F3	4 ± 0.1

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Figure 4.1: Result of pH test.

4.3 Irritation Test

Table 4.3 Irritation Test.

Sr. No	Formulation	Observation
1	F1	No irritation
2	F2	No irritation
3	F3	No irritation

4.4 Foam Retention

Table 4.4 Forming index.

Sr. No	Formulation	Foaming Index
1	F1	25
2	F2	20
3	F3	16.5

Figure 4.2: Forming index.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, The aim of the study was to formulate different herbal into a soap for moisturizing and glowing activity of the skin. This soap contain properties of neem, Aloe Vera, Tulsi, ayurvedic cosmetics is very helpful and does not give it side effects. Ayurvedic cosmetics are also known as herbal cosmetics. The plant used in soap preparation is able to soft the skin epidermis enhances greater penetration remove acne as well as promotes healing and resolution in quickly in time.

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